

cmfg-gym: A Reproducible Research Instrument for Partially Observable Dynamic Scheduling in Cloud Manufacturing

David Chambers^a, Thorsten Lammers^a, Kun Yu^b, Nathan Chambers^c

^a*School of Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering, University of Technology Sydney, Sydney, Australia*

^b*The Data Science Institute, University of Technology Sydney, Sydney, Australia*

^c*Ergosphere.ai, Sydney, Australia*

Abstract

Deep reinforcement learning (DRL) has become an increasingly common approach to dynamic Cloud Manufacturing (CMfg) scheduling, yet cumulative comparison remains weak because studies rarely operate on like-for-like problem worlds. Across the recent CMfg-DRL literature, problem formulations vary materially, environment disclosure is uneven, and partial observability is often left implicit. In that setting, further algorithmic novelty alone yields limited cumulative knowledge. This paper addresses that methodological bottleneck by introducing and validating a reusable research instrument. We first derive the Unified Cloud Manufacturing Scheduling Model (UCSM), a four-layer architecture spanning demand, supply, logistics, and control, and show how recurring CMfg scheduling constructs can be represented within a common ontology. We then operationalise that architecture as **cmfg-gym**, a Gymnasium-compatible environment with serialisable scenarios, explicit stochastic controls, and an agent-facing formulation expressed as a partially observable Markov decision process. Reproducibility is anchored to explicit artefact surfaces: an anchored repository version, fixed flagship scenario files, and a fixed training/evaluation/test seed contract. To test whether the instrument is scientifically usable, we validate one flagship **cmfg-gym** family across service-composition and task-scheduling regimes with sequential and DAG job structures using two standard DRL probes (PPO and DDQN). Under held-out seed-paired evaluation, no simple heuristic dominates; PPO beats the strongest per-seed heuristic across all four configurations; DDQN is competitive but mixed against that comparator; and PPO separates clearly

from DDQN, with the strongest discrimination appearing in task scheduling. The claim is deliberately bounded. We do not establish a field-wide benchmark ladder or a universal reward-design result. Rather, we show that one explicit, reproducible CMfg environment family is non-trivial, learnable, and sufficiently discerning to support later like-for-like DRL comparison.

Keywords: cloud manufacturing, deep reinforcement learning, benchmark environments, partial observability, reproducibility

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1. Introduction

Dynamic scheduling is central to Cloud Manufacturing (CMfg) because the operating model couples distributed resources, heterogeneous service providers, transport effects, uncertain arrivals, and time-varying availability. Those properties make CMfg a natural target for deep reinforcement learning (DRL). Unlike static optimisation methods that solve one fully specified instance at a time, DRL aims to learn a policy that can react online to realised system dynamics. In a setting where disruptions, logistics delays, and workload variation are operationally important, that shift from repeated re-optimisation to learned sequential control is appealing.

Yet the present CMfg-DRL literature is growing faster in volume than in cumulative reliability. Our review of 21 CMfg-DRL studies published between 2015 and April 2025 shows that results are still hard to compare on a like-for-like basis. Many studies instantiate materially different problem worlds under the same broad label of “CMfg scheduling”. Representative studies differ in job structure, decision locus, logistics treatment, stochastic dynamics, and observability assumptions [5, 2, 17, 19, 4, 20]. A provider-selection problem with sequential jobs and implicit logistics is not the same empirical object as a service-level scheduler with DAG precedence, explicit transport, and stochastic disruption.

The same review reveals a second obstacle: weak environment reproducibility. Many papers report promising results without exposing enough concrete environmental detail to allow close reconstruction. Missing units, omitted logistics parameters, partially specified stochastic processes, or paper-specific

workload generators make later comparison difficult to audit [2, 5, 6, 3]. In a field without widely adopted public datasets, the environment itself is part of the scientific contribution. When the environment remains under-specified, later claims about algorithmic superiority are anchored to private experimental worlds.

A third problem is architectural. CMfg scheduling is often operationally partially observable: resource status may be delayed or incomplete, disruptions are only revealed through their effects, and the consequences of assignments unfold over time through processing and logistics. Despite this, most CMfg-DRL studies still use MDP-style formulations with feed-forward agents, while explicit recurrent treatment remains uncommon. That mismatch matters because it shapes which policies can be represented and how later architectural comparisons should be interpreted.

Taken together, these issues imply that the immediate bottleneck in CMfg-DRL is methodological rather than purely algorithmic. Before the field can accumulate stronger comparative claims, it needs a common empirical instrument. That instrument should be a reusable environment whose world model is explicit, whose stochastic contract is reproducible, and whose agent interface is consistent with the problem’s partial observability. It must also be validated operationally rather than merely released as software.

This paper addresses that need in three steps. First, we derive the Unified Cloud Manufacturing Scheduling Model (UCSM), a literature-grounded architecture that organises recurring CMfg constructs into four layers: demand, supply, logistics, and control. Second, we operationalise that architecture as `cmfg-gym`, a parametrically controlled, serialisable, Gymnasium-compatible environment that exposes CMfg scheduling as a partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP). In that sense, `cmfg-gym` is intended not just as reusable code, but as a computer-integrated manufacturing research instrument with an explicit decision interface and reproducibility surface. Third, we evaluate whether one flagship `cmfg-gym` family is suitable for later comparative DRL research under a fixed held-out protocol.

For a computer-integrated manufacturing audience, that instrument layer matters because it turns a loosely specified scheduling problem into a reusable decision environment with explicit entities, interfaces, and stochastic controls. In practical terms, it enables later studies to compare dispatching, control, and learning policies on a shared operational model of distributed providers, jobs, and logistics rather than on private simulators with drifting assumptions.

The intended practical analogue is a cloud-manufacturing platform or

distributed production network in which a coordinator assigns work across geographically separated providers under incomplete state information, transport delay, and fluctuating local availability. In that setting, `cmfg-gym` is meant to support early-stage decisions such as screening candidate dispatching or learning policies, checking whether partial observability materially changes the control problem, and deciding which policy families merit higher-fidelity plant-specific follow-on study. The flagship family is parameterised so that its magnitudes admit a physically interpretable reading in distance, time, transport-speed, and cost terms. The native simulation scale remains abstract, so this should be read as bounded operational interpretability rather than as a literal declaration of industrial units or as formal empirical calibration.

The contribution is methodological and deliberately bounded. The paper asks a narrow question: can one explicit, literature-derived, reproducible CMfg environment family function as a scientifically usable benchmark instrument?

This paper makes three contributions. First, it introduces UCSM, a unified conceptual architecture for recurring CMfg scheduling structure without collapsing the literature into one narrow formulation. Second, it operationalises that architecture as `cmfg-gym`, with serialisable scenarios, explicit stochastic controls, and reproducibility anchored to concrete artefact surfaces rather than prose alone. Third, it validates one flagship environment family across service-composition and task-scheduling regimes using PPO and DDQN as representative probes. That validation shows that the instrument is non-trivial, learnable, and sufficiently discerning for later like-for-like comparative work.

In field terms, the paper contributes the missing instrument layer. Its purpose is not to advance one more local scheduler on one more private simulator, but to make later CMfg-DRL comparisons cumulative, auditable, and grounded in a shared empirical object for computer-integrated manufacturing research.

2. Related Work and Design Requirements

2.1. Review scope and purpose

This paper is motivated by a systematic review of 21 DRL-based CMfg scheduling studies published between 2015 and April 2025. The role of this section is not to catalogue every algorithmic variation in that corpus. Its purpose is to establish the field conditions that make a benchmark instrument necessary. Read as a whole, the literature already contains enough recurring

structure to support a unified model, but not enough standardisation or reproducibility to support reliable like-for-like comparison. Three issues recur most clearly: formulation heterogeneity, weak environment disclosure, and an unresolved mismatch between partial observability and the interfaces through which agents are trained.

2.2. Recurring modelling structure

Despite their heterogeneity, the reviewed studies share a recognisable modelling core. Across the corpus, CMfg scheduling is repeatedly built from the same broad components: jobs or orders arriving from demand; distributed providers, services, or machines on the supply side; logistics or transport effects coupling geographically separated execution; and a control process that assigns, sequences, or dispatches work over time. These recurring components are what make a unified conceptual model possible.

The commonality is easiest to see along three axes: job structure, decision locus, and operational realism. Jobs may be represented as sequential chains, DAG workflows, hierarchical cloud-edge decompositions, or more classical flexible job-shop structures [2, 5, 4, 17, 19, 7]. The decision locus also varies: some studies act at provider or enterprise level, whereas others select service instances, machines, or dispatching rules [18, 8, 2, 21, 20]. Logistics and dynamics recur as well, even when handled unevenly. Across the review corpus, some studies model transport time and cost explicitly, while others abstract logistics away; similarly, “dynamic” may refer to stochastic arrivals, fluctuating availability, machine breakdowns, or processing-time noise [8, 9, 21, 7, 19].

These common patterns matter for two reasons. First, they show that CMfg scheduling is not conceptually incoherent; there is enough recurring structure to justify a unifying architecture. Second, they show why algorithmic performance is inseparable from the world being controlled. A benchmark paper therefore has to do two things at once: capture the recurring CMfg core and keep benchmark-specific modelling choices explicit.

2.3. Why current studies are hard to compare

The central standardisation problem is that the literature shares vocabulary without sharing a sufficiently common empirical object. Many papers report results under the same broad label of “CMfg scheduling”, but the underlying world model differs materially across studies. The result is that the literature often compares unlike with unlike, even when the reporting language sounds superficially similar.

The review also shows that environment disclosure remains uneven. Some studies demonstrate that detailed reporting is possible by tabulating provider capabilities, processing ranges, logistics coefficients, stochastic settings, and instance-generation rules [8, 9, 11, 4, 7]. Those papers establish an important point: in CMfg-DRL, the environment can be documented closely enough for later reuse when it is treated as part of the scientific contribution rather than as hidden scaffolding.

Even so, that standard is not typical. Across the 21-paper corpus, 13 studies are environmentally under-specified, 4 are only partially specified, and only 4 provide full disclosure of the core ingredients needed for like-for-like reconstruction. Missing units, omitted logistics coefficients, loosely described stochastic processes, and private workload generators are especially common [2, 5, 6, 3]. In a field without established public datasets, this means that many published results remain tied to local simulators that cannot easily be audited or recreated.

A benchmark contribution therefore has to address standardisation and reproducibility together. It is not enough to expose a generic agent–environment API. The problem world, scenario contract, observability boundary, and stochastic controls also need to be explicit.

2.4. The infrastructure gap

The current infrastructure landscape has two useful but incomplete pieces. At one end, general RL tooling such as OpenAI Gym and Gymnasium standardises the agent–environment API [1, 14]. That interoperability layer is valuable, but it does not solve the CMfg problem-definition gap. A generic API does not say what entities exist, what dynamics are active, what is observable, or how one study’s scenario should be reproduced by another.

At the other end, the CMfg literature already contains many local simulators. The problem is that these are usually paper-specific instruments rather than shared field infrastructure. The review corpus shows that most studies define their own environment assumptions, parameter ranges, and stochastic contracts, and that most do not expose enough concrete detail for close reconstruction. The field therefore has many environments, but not yet a common instrument.

This is the gap `cmfg-gym` is intended to fill: a domain-specific, serialisable, Gymnasium-compatible research tool whose world model and reproducibility surfaces are explicit enough for reuse, audit, and later comparative study.

2.5. Partial observability as a design requirement

The third pattern is architectural rather than purely descriptive. CMfg scheduling is often effectively partially observable. Provider state may be delayed or incomplete, disruptions are latent until revealed operationally, and the consequences of assignments are delayed by both processing and logistics. Yet explicit recurrent treatment remains rare. Only 4 of the 21 reviewed studies use recurrent mechanisms directly, whereas most rely on feed-forward agents under MDP-style formulations [17, 2, 4, 7].

For a benchmark paper, this is not a side note. If the environment is operationally partially observable, then the tool should make that explicit by clearly defining what belongs to the latent world state, what the agent observes, what is masked, and what remains hidden. Otherwise later algorithmic comparisons risk conflating model capacity with unspoken interface assumptions.

2.6. Design requirements

Taken together, these review findings define the design requirements for a CMfg benchmark instrument.

First, the field needs a unified conceptual model that captures recurring CMfg scheduling structure without collapsing the literature into one narrow formulation. Second, it needs an executable environment whose instances are serialisable and reproducible through explicit artefact anchors rather than prose alone. Third, it needs interoperability with standard DRL tooling while retaining CMfg-specific structure. Fourth, it needs an agent-facing formulation that treats partial observability explicitly rather than implicitly. Fifth, it needs validation evidence showing that the tool is scientifically usable: not trivial, not unlearnable, and not so saturated that it cannot support controlled comparative work under a held-out protocol.

These requirements define the role of the present paper. It introduces and validates `cmfg-gym` as a reusable research instrument rather than claiming a final benchmark ladder. From an applied CMfg viewpoint, these requirements matter because a reusable benchmark is useful only if later studies can compare policy choices on a stable operational model rather than on locally redefined provider networks, workload generators, and logistics assumptions.

3. The Unified Cloud Manufacturing Scheduling Model

3.1. Role of the model

The literature review shows that CMfg scheduling studies differ widely in their concrete formulations, yet repeatedly instantiate the same underlying world components. UCSM is intended to capture that recurring structure. It is therefore a conceptual synthesis, not a claim that one formulation should replace all others. Its purpose is to provide a stable architectural language for comparison, tool construction, and explicit scoping.

Two levels need to be distinguished from the outset. UCSM defines the common architecture of the scheduling world; `cmfg-gym` then instantiates one bounded operational version of that world for executable benchmarking. This distinction matters because a unified model should identify what the literature shares, whereas a benchmark environment must make its own assumptions and constraints explicit.

3.2. What is being unified

Across the reviewed CMfg literature, formulations differ in job structure, decision locus, logistics treatment, and stochastic assumptions. Some papers schedule sequential task chains, others DAG workflows or more classical flexible job-shop abstractions. Some act at provider level, others at service or machine level. Logistics may be explicit, implicit, or omitted altogether, and dynamic behaviour may arise from stochastic arrivals, disruptions, or processing-time variation. These differences are substantial enough to prevent direct like-for-like comparison.

At the same time, the literature repeatedly instantiates the same broad components: work enters from demand, heterogeneous resources are organised on the supply side, geographically distributed execution induces logistics costs and delays, and a control process assigns work over time. UCSM unifies those recurring components into one common architecture while leaving benchmark-specific implementation choices explicit. In that sense, “unified” does not mean “one universal CMfg instance class”. It means one stable architectural decomposition within which different CMfg scheduling regimes can be expressed transparently.

3.3. Demand, supply, logistics, and control

The demand layer represents the work entering the system. It treats jobs as containers of subtasks linked by a generic precedence relation, allowing the

Figure 1: Unified Cloud Manufacturing Scheduling Model (UCSM): four-layer architecture mapping recurring literature constructs to demand, supply, logistics, and control.

same model to host sequential structures, richer DAG workflows, and more classical shop-floor variants [2, 5, 17, 19, 7].

The supply layer represents distributed processing resources. Some studies act at provider level; others act at service or machine level [18, 8, 2]. UCSM reconciles these views by structuring supply hierarchically: manufacturing service providers contain one or more manufacturing services.

The logistics layer captures the distributional coupling that distinguishes CMfg from co-located scheduling. Depending on the formulation, this may include transport time, transport cost, routing effects, internal material movement, or data-transfer costs [9, 21, 16]. Treating logistics as a first-class layer gives the model a principled place to house these variations rather than burying them inside processing assumptions.

The control layer represents scheduling intelligence. In some papers the agent assigns work directly to providers or services; in others it coordinates lower-level resource interactions or selects among composite decision rules [2, 18, 4, 7, 17]. UCSM therefore defines control abstractly as a decision interface rather than fixing one algorithmic locus of action at conceptual level.

Table 1: Representative mapping from literature constructs to UCSM layers.

Layer	Representative constructs in the literature
Demand	jobs, orders, workflows, subtasks, precedence graphs, sequential chains, DAGs
Supply	providers, enterprises, manufacturing services, machines, capabilities, capacities
Logistics	transport time, transport cost, routing, AGV movement, data transfer
Control	DRL agents, dispatching-rule selectors, hyper-heuristics, coordination policies

3.4. Benchmark operationalisation

To support executable benchmarking, `cmfg-gym` instantiates UCSM as a bounded scheduling world defined on a finite discrete horizon $t = 0, \dots, H$. The formalisation below makes explicit the entities, stochastic processes, optimisation target, feasibility conditions, and agent-facing interface required by the benchmark. Unless otherwise noted, this section describes the operational formulation used by `cmfg-gym` and the flagship family in this paper rather than the full space of conceivable CMfg formulations. For readability, the notation uses job-first indexing (i, k) for subtask quantities throughout.

3.4.1. Entities and stochastic dynamics

At the operational level, the supply side is a set of providers $p \in \mathcal{P}$, each defined by location, internal services, and a disruption profile:

$$\text{MSP}_p = (\mathbf{g}_p, \mathcal{S}_p, \lambda_p, \rho_p, \mu_p^{\min}, \mu_p^{\text{maj}}). \quad (1)$$

Each service $j \in \mathcal{S}_p$ is modelled as

$$\text{MS}_{p,j} = (\tau_{p,j}, c_{p,j}, \eta_{p,j}, \nu_{p,j}, \kappa_{p,j}, q_{p,j}, b_{p,j}), \quad (2)$$

capturing service type, processing cost rate, efficiency, processing variance, capacity, intrinsic quality, and current occupancy.

Demand enters the system as jobs $i \in \mathcal{J}$:

$$\text{job}_i = (r_i, d_i, \mathbf{g}_i^{\text{del}}, \mathcal{O}_i, G_i), \quad G_i = (\mathcal{O}_i, E_i), \quad (3)$$

Table 2: Nomenclature for the CMfg scheduling and DRL formulation used by cmfg-gym (1 of 2).

Symbol	Meaning	Symbol	Meaning
\mathcal{P}	set of manufacturing service providers (MSPs)	\mathcal{S}_p	set of manufacturing services (MSs) offered by provider p
\mathcal{J}	set of jobs appearing within an episode	\mathcal{O}_i	set of subtasks belonging to job i
$G_i = (\mathcal{O}_i, E_i)$	precedence graph for job i	$\text{pred}_{i,k}$	predecessors of subtask (i, k) in G_i
H	episode horizon	r_i, d_i	release time and due time of job i
f^{due}	scenario-level due-date scaler	A_t, α	job-arrival indicator and arrival probability
\mathbf{g}_p	spatial coordinates of provider p	$\mathbf{g}_i^{\text{del}}$	delivery location of completed job i
$\tau_{i,k}$	required service type of subtask (i, k)	$\tau_{p,j}$	service type supplied by MS (p, j)
$u_{i,k}$	workload or processing units of subtask (i, k)	$\kappa_{p,j}$	capacity of MS (p, j)
$c_{p,j}$	processing cost per unit time of MS (p, j)	$\eta_{p,j}$	efficiency of MS (p, j)
$\nu_{p,j}$	processing-time variance parameter of MS (p, j)	$z_{p,j}$	multiplicative processing-time noise factor
$q_{p,j}$	intrinsic quality parameter of MS (p, j)	$q_{i,k}$	delivered quality realised by subtask (i, k)
$b_{p,j}$	busy indicator for MS (p, j)	λ_p	disruption-event rate attached to provider p
ρ_p	probability that a provider disruption is minor	$\mu_p^{\text{min}}, \mu_p^{\text{maj}}$	mean minor and major disruption durations
$N_p(t)$	cumulative disruption-count process for provider p	v_L, c_L	logistics speed and logistics unit-cost factor

where \mathcal{O}_i is the set of subtasks and G_i may be either a sequential chain or a directed acyclic graph. Each subtask $(i, k) \in \mathcal{O}_i$ is defined by

$$o_{i,k} = (\tau_{i,k}, u_{i,k}), \quad (4)$$

and becomes schedulable only when all predecessors in

$$\text{pred}_{i,k} = \{o_{i,h} \in \mathcal{O}_i : (o_{i,h}, o_{i,k}) \in E_i\} \quad (5)$$

have completed both processing and any required logistics movement.

Some operational choices in the benchmark are intentionally specific to the flagship family. For example, due dates are generated on release as

$$d_i = r_i + f^{\text{due}} \sum_{o_{i,k} \in \mathcal{O}_i} u_{i,k}. \quad (6)$$

This is not asserted as a universal CMfg rule; it is the current due-date contract used by the environment family validated in this paper. Job generation itself is stochastic:

$$A_t \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\alpha), \quad (7)$$

Table 3: Nomenclature for the CMfg scheduling and DRL formulation used by cmfg-gym (2 of 2).

Symbol	Meaning	Symbol	Meaning
$d(\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2)$	Euclidean distance between two locations	$\ell_{i,k}$	logistics time incurred by subtask (i, k)
$c_{i,k}^{\log}$	logistics cost incurred by subtask (i, k)	$p_{i,k}^{(p,j)}$	realised processing time of subtask (i, k) on MS (p, j)
$c_{i,k}^{\text{proc}}$	realised processing cost of subtask (i, k)	c_i^{del}	final delivery logistics cost of completed job i
Q_i	composite QoS score of completed job i	$S_i^{\text{time}}, S_i^{\text{cost}}, S_i^{\text{qual}}$	normalised time, cost, and quality components of Q_i
w_t, w_c, w_q	weights for time, cost, and quality in QoS	F_i, C_i	flow time and completion time of job i
T_{\min}, T_{\max}	bounds for time-score normalisation	C_{\min}, C_{\max}	bounds for cost-score normalisation
C_i^{tot}	total job cost including processing and logistics	δ_i	tardiness ratio of job i
C_H	jobs completed by horizon H	$\pi, J(\pi)$	scheduling policy and its expected return
\mathcal{M}	environment POMDP	\mathcal{X}, Ω	latent state space and observation space
\mathbf{o}_t	observation vector at time t	\bar{t}, d	normalised time feature and observation dimension
$\phi_t^{\text{msp}}, \phi_t^{\text{ms}}, \phi_t^{\text{job}}, \phi_t^{\text{sub}}$	provider, service, job, and subtask feature blocks in \mathbf{o}_t	\mathcal{A}, a_t	action space and selected action
$m_t(a)$	binary action-feasibility mask	$\mathbf{m}_t^{\text{obs}}$	observation-validity mask for padded entities
$P^{\max}, S^{\max}, J^{\max}, O^{\max}$	scenario maxima for providers, services, jobs, and subtasks	T, O, R, γ	POMDP transition, observation, reward maps, and discount factor
R_t	reward at time t		

so a new job template is sampled and released at step t whenever $A_t = 1$.

In the present operationalisation, the logistics layer is represented by a single service with speed v_L and unit cost c_L . Moving subtask (i, k) between two locations \mathbf{g}_1 and \mathbf{g}_2 incurs

$$c_{i,k}^{\log}(\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2) = u_{i,k} c_L d(\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2), \quad (8)$$

$$\ell_{i,k}(\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2) = \frac{d(\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2)}{v_L}. \quad (9)$$

This simplified logistics layer is again a bounded benchmark choice rather than the only admissible realisation of the UCSM logistics layer. In practical terms, this bounded logistics model stands in for a distributed production setting in which jobs move between physically separated providers or service cells and transport affects both delay and cost. Detailed routing, fleet management, and

multi-leg handling are outside the present benchmark scope. The benchmark uses an abstract grid-and-tick scale whose magnitudes admit a physically interpretable reading in distance, delay, transport-speed, and cost terms. That improves operational readability, but it is not presented as a calibrated transport model or as a formal declaration of native industrial units.

Processing time is stochastic and depends on workload, service efficiency, and a service-specific variance parameter:

$$p_{i,k}^{(p,j)} = \left[\max \left(\left[\frac{u_{i,k}}{\eta_{p,j}} \right] z_{p,j}, 1 \right) \right], \quad (10)$$

$$z_{p,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(1, \nu_{p,j}), \quad c_{i,k}^{\text{proc}} = p_{i,k}^{(p,j)} c_{p,j}.$$

Delivered quality for a completed subtask is inherited from the executing service, so $q_{i,k} = q_{p,j}$. Provider-originating disruption events follow

$$N_p(t + \Delta) - N_p(t) \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_p \Delta), \quad (11)$$

with each event minor with probability ρ_p and major otherwise. Minor and major downtimes are sampled from distributions with means μ_p^{min} and μ_p^{maj} , respectively. Processing is non-pre-emptive except when a major disruption forces the current subtask back into the assignment pool.

3.4.2. Objective and feasibility

The operational scheduling problem is to learn a policy π that maximises expected episode-level Quality of Service (QoS):

$$J(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_\pi \left[\sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}_H} Q_i \right]. \quad (12)$$

For each completed job i , the environment aggregates time, cost, and quality:

$$Q_i = w_t S_i^{\text{time}} + w_c S_i^{\text{cost}} + w_q S_i^{\text{qual}}. \quad (13)$$

The time term uses flow time $F_i = C_i - r_i$ and a tardiness penalty,

$$\delta_i = \left[\frac{C_i - d_i}{d_i - r_i} \right]_+, \quad (14)$$

$$S_i^{\text{time}} = \frac{T_{\max} - F_i}{T_{\max} - T_{\min}} (1 - \delta_i), \quad (15)$$

the cost term normalises total realised job cost,

$$C_i^{\text{tot}} = \sum_{o_{i,k} \in \mathcal{O}_i} (c_{i,k}^{\text{proc}} + c_{i,k}^{\text{log}}) + c_i^{\text{del}}, \quad (16)$$

$$S_i^{\text{cost}} = \frac{C_{\max} - C_i^{\text{tot}}}{C_{\max} - C_{\min}}, \quad (17)$$

and the quality term is the mean delivered subtask quality,

$$S_i^{\text{qual}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{O}_i|} \sum_{o_{i,k} \in \mathcal{O}_i} q_{i,k}. \quad (18)$$

Operational feasibility is enforced through precedence, compatibility, capacity, exclusivity, and availability. A service-level assignment (p, j) is feasible for subtask (i, k) at time t only if

$$\tau_{p,j} = \tau_{i,k}, \quad u_{i,k} \leq \kappa_{p,j}, \quad b_{p,j} = 0, \quad (19)$$

all predecessors in $\text{pred}_{i,k}$ have completed, the subtask is not in transit, and the service is not currently disabled by disruption.

The benchmark supports two control regimes. In task-scheduling mode the policy chooses an individual service (p, j) directly. In service-composition mode the policy chooses a provider p , after which the provider dispatches the subtask to the best currently feasible internal service. This factorisation is deliberate: it preserves a provider-level action space while keeping intra-provider behaviour explicit and reproducible.

3.4.3. Agent-facing POMDP

To support DRL experimentation, `cmfg-gym` exposes the operational scheduling problem induced by UCSM as a POMDP,

$$\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{X}, \Omega, \mathcal{A}, T, O, R, \gamma), \quad (20)$$

rather than as a fully observed MDP. Partial observability arises because the world contains latent disruption dynamics, delayed logistics effects, stochastic processing variation, and no direct access to future trajectory information.

The latent state space \mathcal{X} contains the full CMfg world state, including active jobs, provider queues, service occupancy, disruption processes, and transit processes. The agent does not observe \mathcal{X} directly. Instead, it receives a fixed-length observation vector

$$\mathbf{o}_t = [\bar{t}, \phi_t^{\text{msp}}, \phi_t^{\text{ms}}, \phi_t^{\text{job}}, \phi_t^{\text{sub}}] \in \mathbb{R}^d. \quad (21)$$

Table 4: Observation components exposed to the DRL agent in `cmfg-gym`.

Group	Components	Dimension
Time	normalised simulation time $\bar{t} = t/H$	1
Providers	provider coordinates for each padded provider slot	$2P^{\max}$
Services	service type, capacity, cost, efficiency, quality, and busy flag for each padded service slot	$6P^{\max}S^{\max}$
Jobs	delivery coordinates and due date for each padded active-job slot	$3J^{\max}$
Subtasks	next-action flag, current location, workload, successor mask, required service type, and four status flags for each padded subtask slot	$J^{\max}O^{\max}(9 + O^{\max})$

The observation concatenates normalised time, provider coordinates, service attributes and busy flags, active-job attributes, and subtask-level features including workload, required service type, precedence information, and status flags. Padding to scenario-defined maxima produces a constant observation dimension d .

The resulting observation dimension is therefore

$$d = 1 + 2P^{\max} + 6P^{\max}S^{\max} + 3J^{\max} + J^{\max}O^{\max}(9 + O^{\max}). \quad (22)$$

For the flagship setting $P^{\max} = 5$, $S^{\max} = 10$, $J^{\max} = 5$, and $O^{\max} = 5$, Eq. (22) gives $d = 676$. The environment also provides an observation-validity mask

$$\mathbf{m}_t^{\text{obs}} \in \{0, 1\}^d, \quad (23)$$

which identifies non-padded entries in the flattened representation.

The observation intentionally omits parts of the latent world state, including internal disruption state, remaining downtime, exact disruption and variance parameters, future stochastic outcomes, detailed remaining transit time, and explicit history beyond the current feature vector. Partial observability is therefore not an accidental by-product of implementation; it is part of the benchmark contract.

The action space depends on the problem type:

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{P}, & \text{service composition,} \\ \bigcup_{p \in \mathcal{P}} \mathcal{S}_p, & \text{task scheduling.} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

At each time step, the environment provides a binary feasibility mask

$$m_t(a) = \mathbb{I}\{a \text{ is feasible at time } t\}, \quad (25)$$

so policy optimisation is restricted to assignments that satisfy the feasibility conditions above. In service-composition mode, choosing $a_t = p$ sends the currently schedulable subtask to provider p 's FIFO queue, and the provider dispatches the queue head to the feasible internal service with the highest efficiency. In task-scheduling mode, the action specifies the service (p, j) directly.

The reward contract used by the benchmark family in this paper is sparse and episodic:

$$R_t = \begin{cases} 0, & t < H, \\ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}_H} Q_i, & t = H. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

This choice aligns the RL objective directly with the episode-level QoS objective in (12). The paper does not claim that sparse episodic reward is universally preferable; it claims only that this reward definition is explicit, reproducible, and appropriate for the benchmark family validated here.

The current operationalisation further assumes fixed provider coordinates during an episode, a single logistics layer parameterised by (v_L, c_L) , and at most one agent assignment decision per time step. These assumptions keep the world bounded enough for reproducible comparison without removing the core CMfg trade-offs among time, cost, quality, distribution, and uncertainty. Read operationally, these choices make the flagship family closest to an early-stage evaluation setting in which provider locations and service capabilities are known at planning time, logistics is represented at aggregate transfer level, and the control problem is repeated assignment under uncertain arrivals, processing variation, and disruption. The intended claim is therefore one of bounded physical interpretability and face validity, not that every plant-specific constraint, unit relationship, or dispatch rule has been empirically calibrated for deployment.

4. cmfg-gym as a Benchmark Instrument

4.1. Environment design and reproducibility

`cmfg-gym` is intended as an executable research instrument rather than as a one-off simulator. A central environment class manages dynamic jobs on the demand side, provider and service objects on the supply side, and logistics objects on the distribution side, while exposing a standard `gymnasium.Env` interface to the learning agent. This interoperability matters because a

benchmark is useful only if it can be reused easily across established RL tooling.

The central reproducibility surface is the scenario object. Rather than hiding the definition of an instance class inside generator code, `cmfg-gym` uses serialisable scenario dataclasses that encapsulate provider topology, job structure, service attributes, stochastic-process settings, and environment toggles. Scenarios can therefore be saved, shared, and reloaded as JSON files.

That scenario system also preserves configurability without sacrificing ontology. Researchers can toggle disruptions and production variance, choose between service-composition and task-scheduling regimes, and vary job structure between sequential and DAG settings while remaining inside the same world model. A single seed governs job arrivals, disruptions, processing variability, and related dynamics, enabling seed-paired comparison under matched realised stochastic conditions. For an industry-facing reader, the practical value of this structure is that alternative dispatching or learning policies can be stress-tested on the same explicit provider–job–logistics world before any higher-fidelity digital-twin or site-specific integration work is attempted.

Reproducibility in this paper is anchored to explicit artefact surfaces rather than to prose alone. The public codebase is maintained at <https://github.com/ergosphere-ai/cmfg-gym>. For the flagship family, the minimum reproducibility unit is the environment package, the repo-level scenario JSON files that instantiate it, and the fixed training/evaluation/test seed contract. Table 5 records the concrete anchor used in this paper. In practical terms, the public Paper 1 reproduction surface consists of the anchored repository version, the canonical flagship scenario, the Paper 1 witness copy listed below, the retained published probe checkpoints, and the bounded workflow-validation paths documented in the companion repository. It does not claim a full exact-from-scratch recomputation of every published Paper 1 statistic from the public repo alone.

4.2. Flagship environment family

The empirical evidence in this paper is intentionally bounded to one flagship family derived from the `slc_balanced.json` scenario and its paired Paper 1 witness copy `paper_artifacts/paper1/slc_balanced_witness.json`. The family is small enough for systematic comparison while still forcing real trade-offs between time, cost, and quality. Core settings are explicit: five manufacturing service providers, thirty-four services spanning ten service types, up to five concurrent jobs, three to five subtasks per job, stochastic

Table 5: Artefact anchor for the flagship `cmfg-gym` family used in this paper.

Element	Anchor
Repository	https://github.com/ergosphere-ai/cmfg-gym
Anchored repository version	0.1.0 (dated 2026-04-04)
Fixed flagship artefacts	<code>slc_balanced.json</code> and <code>paper_artifacts/paper1/slc_balanced_witness.json</code>
Shared SHA256 digest	F387A1CE6FB351035ADBFA567F1C76B02089FFE527E22CBED963305EDBE3FFAC
Train seed base	0
Evaluation seed block start	10^6
Held-out test seed block start	2×10^6
Runtime environment	Python 3.9.5; NumPy 2.0.2; Gymnasium 1.0.0; PyTorch 2.6.0+cu126; Tianshou 0.5.1; Windows 11; RTX 3090

arrivals, disruptions, production variability, and a horizon of 2880 decision steps. The flagship family is therefore best read as a stylised small-to-medium distributed provider network. Its purpose is to test whether the instrument supports meaningful trade-offs among time, cost, quality, and uncertainty. Its magnitudes admit a physically interpretable reading, but the simulator still operates on abstract native scales. It is not intended as a literal model of one specific industrial installation or as a statistically representative industrial sample.

Within that family, four controlled configurations are used: service composition with sequential jobs, service composition with DAG jobs, task scheduling with sequential jobs, and task scheduling with DAG jobs. The role of this family is narrower than the role of UCSM or of `cmfg-gym` as a whole. UCSM defines the conceptual architecture, `cmfg-gym` provides the executable instrument, and the flagship family is one explicit instantiation used to test whether that instrument is scientifically usable under a fixed protocol. The purpose of this bounded family is not to stand in for the whole CMfg design space. Its purpose is to define the scope of the present evidence clearly enough for later comparative work.

The flagship instance was not selected rhetorically to favour one baseline. It was post-processed with an evolutionary balancing procedure designed to keep strong heuristic baselines competitive while avoiding dominance across the paired training, evaluation, and test settings used in this study. Three heuristic policies (highest efficiency, lowest cost, and highest quality) were evaluated on both service-composition and task-scheduling views of the scenario, and candidate instances were scored by a composite of heuristic win-rate imbalance and policy decision diversity. The result is therefore a deliberately balanced flagship instance rather than an arbitrary synthetic example, and the balancing

Figure 2: High-level class architecture of `cmfg-gym`, showing the central environment, scenario object, and the main environment entities.

criterion was used to avoid both heuristic-dominated triviality and DRL-favouring triviality rather than to advantage any DRL family.

4.3. Reward choice

Equation (26) defines the reward contract used by the benchmark family in this paper. That sparse episodic design was not chosen rhetorically. A fixed A2C reward-variant study compared it against three dense alternatives and found that the sparse episodic reward produced the strongest performance under the tested setup.

That evidence is deliberately bounded. The reward comparison used one learner family only (A2C), a fixed episode horizon of 2880, five random seeds, and identical scenario realisations per seed across all reward variants. The four tested schemes were sparse episodic reward, dense job-completion reward, dense assignment expected-value reward, and a hybrid dense reward combining assignment-time and completion signals. The result therefore

Table 6: Flagship environment family used for validation.

Element	Setting
Simulation horizon	2880 decision steps
Providers	5 MSPs
Services	34 services across 10 service types
Concurrent jobs	up to 5 active jobs
Job size	3-5 subtasks per job
Spatial extent	16 × 16 grid
Arrival process	stochastic, per-step arrival probability 0.015
Structural variants	service composition or task scheduling; sequential or DAG jobs
Dynamic variation	disruptions and production variance enabled
QoS weighting	time = 1, cost = 1, quality = 1

Table 7: Reward-variant comparison under a fixed A2C setup.

Reward scheme	Win rate	QoS diff
Sparse episodic	91.5%	+0.259
Dense job completion	86.8%	+0.199
Dense assignment EV	86.3%	+0.184
Hybrid dense	75.5%	+0.129

Setup: A2C; episode horizon 2880; 5 random seeds; identical scenario realisations per seed across reward variants.

supports a benchmark design choice for this environment family; it is not a universal dense-versus-sparse theorem across CMfg or DRL more broadly, and it should not be conflated with the main PPO/DDQN validation evidence in the next section.

5. Validation of the Benchmark Instrument

5.1. Validation goal and allowed claim

The validation stage tests `cmfg-gym` as a research instrument before asking it to carry broader comparative claims. The flagship family, the four controlled configurations, the seed-pairing logic, and the held-out evaluation discipline are fixed in advance. The question is therefore not which algorithm is best in general, but whether the instrument is scientifically usable for later like-for-like CMfg-DRL comparison.

The validation protocol is intentionally strict. Learnability is not assessed against a weak average baseline, but against the strongest deterministic heuristic available on each held-out seed. All substantive comparisons are

seed-paired, so a win means outperforming the comparator under the same realised arrivals, disruptions, and processing variation. Tie-aware win rate and paired QoS margins provide descriptive summaries, while paired Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm correction provide inferential discipline.

For auditability, the validation envelope is deliberately small and explicit: two DRL probes (PPO and DDQN), four controlled configurations, a disjoint 100-seed evaluation block for model selection, and a disjoint 100-seed held-out test block for final inference.

Under this protocol, the validation can support a narrow but important claim: that the flagship `cmfg-gym` family is operationally usable for later comparative DRL research. It does not establish external validity for all CMfg settings, universal reward-design conclusions, or a definitive field leaderboard. For clarity, this validation stage supports the credibility of the benchmark as a comparative research instrument; it is not intended to certify direct production readiness for a specific CMfg deployment.

Three criteria are tested. First, non-triviality: no simple heuristic should dominate across seeds and experiments. Second, learnability: a standard DRL agent should outperform strong heuristic baselines under held-out evaluation. Third, discernment: the environment should reveal meaningful differences between materially different DRL probes rather than collapsing them all into ties.

5.2. Validation probes and protocol

PPO and DDQN are used here as validation probes because they span two established DRL learning regimes while remaining easy to interpret under one fixed protocol. PPO supplies an on-policy actor-critic probe, whereas DDQN supplies an off-policy value-based probe that mirrors common practice in the CMfg-DRL literature. The aim is not to claim that these two agents exhaust the modern DRL design space. Rather, the aim is to show that the environment can support both learning against strong heuristics and controlled separation between materially different method families.

For the algorithm definitions below, let x_t denote the masked observation presented to the agent, a_t the selected valid action, r_t the environment reward, d_{t+1} the termination indicator, and $m_{t+1} = 1 - d_{t+1}$ the continuation mask. Policy-based agents use $\pi_\theta(a \mid x)$ and value functions $V_\psi(x)$; value-based agents use action-values $Q_\theta(x, a)$.

PPO. Proximal Policy Optimisation [13], with GAE-style advantages [12], is an on-policy actor–critic method that stabilises policy improvement through a clipped surrogate. In the present benchmark family, the policy and value networks use feed-forward multilayer perceptrons, invalid actions are removed by feasibility masking before categorical sampling, and updates are performed on masked vector rollouts collected directly from the environment. The optimisation objective is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{PPO}}(\theta, \psi) = & -\mathbb{E}\left[\min\left(r_t(\theta)\hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)\hat{A}_t\right)\right] \\ & + c_v \mathbb{E}\left[(V_\psi(x_t) - \hat{V}_t)^2\right] - c_s \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{H}(\pi_\theta(\cdot | x_t))]. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where $r_t(\theta) = \pi_\theta(a_t | x_t)/\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(a_t | x_t)$, \hat{A}_t is the masked advantage estimate, and \hat{V}_t is the corresponding return target.

DDQN. Double DQN [15], building on the DQN family [10], is an off-policy value-based method that decouples action selection from target evaluation. In *cmf-g-gym*, DDQN uses a feed-forward Q-network and target network, a replay buffer, and epsilon-greedy valid-action selection with feasibility masking. Its target and loss are

$$y_t = r_t + \gamma m_{t+1} Q_{\bar{\theta}}\left(x_{t+1}, \arg \max_{a'} Q_\theta(x_{t+1}, a')\right), \quad (28)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{DDQN}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}\left[(y_t - Q_\theta(x_t, a_t))^2\right]. \quad (29)$$

The target network is updated periodically, while evaluation uses greedy masked action selection under the frozen online network.

Table 8: Validation agents used to test tool usability.

Agent	Regime	Core update	<i>cmf-g-gym</i> implementation	Train/eval mode
PPO	On-policy actor–critic	Clipped surrogate with GAE-style advantages, value loss, and entropy bonus	Two-layer MLP policy/value networks; masked categorical action selection on the common observation and action interface	Trained from vector episodic rollouts; champion chosen on the disjoint evaluation block; frozen greedy masked policy used on the held-out test block
DDQN	Off-policy value-based	Double-DQN target with replay and periodic target-network updates	Two-layer MLP Q-network and target network; epsilon-greedy valid-action selection with feasibility masking	Trained from replayed transitions under the same episode budget; champion chosen on the disjoint evaluation block; frozen greedy masked Q-policy used on the held-out test block

For each of the four flagship configurations, candidate PPO and DDQN models are trained for 15,000 episodes under a common training base seed of 0, with checkpoints every 500 episodes. Candidate selection uses a disjoint 100-seed evaluation block beginning at 10^6 , and all reported validation results are computed on a disjoint 100-seed held-out test block beginning at 2×10^6 . This separation keeps model selection distinct from final inference while preserving seed-paired comparison across all reported results.

Why no recurrent probe appears in this paper. The tool is explicitly designed to support recurrent control, but recurrent validation is intentionally left to later comparative work. Once sequence models are introduced, the experimental object changes: sequence length, burn-in, hidden-state handling, and family-specific recurrent training losses become part of the question. The present paper therefore keeps the validation pair simple and interpretable. The aim here is to show that the environment can support controlled learning and measurable separation under one fixed protocol, not to decide whether recurrence should improve performance.

5.3. Mean performance: context and limitations

In keeping with common DRL reporting practice, we begin by showing mean episodic QoS scores. This provides useful scale information, but in this benchmark it is not a sufficient ranking device. As Table 9 shows, PPO, DDQN, and the strongest heuristic can appear closely clustered when only means are inspected.

On means alone, the methods can look nearly indistinguishable, especially in the more saturated service-composition regimes. The standard deviations already suggest why that reading is unstable: the spread is large relative to the mean differences.

5.4. Per-seed variability and why pairing is required

The reason paired evaluation is necessary becomes clear at the seed level. Figure 3 shows held-out QoS traces for Exp 1 (SC, Seq). Performance order changes materially from seed to seed, so ranking by independent-sample averages obscures the very differences the benchmark needs to reveal.

Table 9: Mean episodic QoS by algorithm across experiments.

Mean episodic QoS scores (\pm s.d.) for PPO, DDQN, and heuristic baselines across the four flagship configurations (held-out test split, 100 seeds). These values provide scale and variance context, but because seed-level variability is high they are not reliable for fine-grained ranking.

Agent	Exp1 (SC, Seq)	Exp2 (SC, DAG)	Exp3 (TS, Seq)	Exp4 (TS, DAG)
PPO	12.50 \pm 0.32	12.46 \pm 0.35	12.51 \pm 0.32	12.46 \pm 0.35
DDQN	12.46 \pm 0.33	12.35 \pm 0.36	12.37 \pm 0.35	12.34 \pm 0.36
Best heuristic	12.431 \pm 0.300	12.395 \pm 0.346	12.332 \pm 0.338	12.283 \pm 0.349
Highest efficiency	12.277 \pm 0.319	12.273 \pm 0.341	12.211 \pm 0.330	12.179 \pm 0.343
Highest quality	12.255 \pm 0.400	12.184 \pm 0.423	12.210 \pm 0.384	12.136 \pm 0.413
Lowest cost	12.346 \pm 0.323	12.321 \pm 0.331	12.194 \pm 0.362	12.164 \pm 0.343
Random	12.118 \pm 0.330	12.079 \pm 0.349	12.110 \pm 0.322	12.079 \pm 0.344

SC: service composition; TS: task scheduling; Seq: sequential; DAG: directed acyclic graph.

Figure 3: Per-seed QoS in Exp 1 (SC, Seq).

Per-seed QoS scores in Exp 1 (SC, Seq) for PPO, DDQN, and the heuristic baselines on the held-out test split (100 seeds). Large inter-seed variability frequently changes the ordering of methods, which is why all substantive comparisons in this paper are seed-paired.

This high inter-seed variance is not merely a nuisance. It is direct evidence that the benchmark is non-trivial in the sense most relevant to comparative

work: no simple fixed heuristic occupies the top of the performance envelope consistently. Formal baseline-dominance testing matches the visual impression, with no heuristic dominating across the four flagship configurations after multiplicity adjustment.

5.5. Learnability: PPO vs strongest heuristic

We test learnability first with PPO against the strongest possible heuristic comparator, defined per seed. If PPO wins against that adversarial baseline under matched realised stochastic conditions, then the environment is not only solvable but learnable in a meaningful comparative sense.

Table 10: PPO vs best heuristic: paired test summary across experiments.

PPO beats the best per-seed heuristic in all four configurations (held-out test split, 100 paired seeds), with positive median margins throughout. The table reports win counts, median paired margins with 95% BCa confidence intervals, and one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank p -values with Holm correction across experiments.

Experiment	Wins	Median margin [95% BCa CI]	Wilc. p
Exp 1 (SC, Seq)	72	0.49% [0.22%, 0.72%]	< 0.001
Exp 2 (SC, DAG)	65	0.56% [0.15%, 0.90%]	< 0.001
Exp 3 (TS, Seq)	87	1.34% [1.05%, 1.63%]	< 0.001
Exp 4 (TS, DAG)	83	1.44% [1.16%, 1.89%]	< 0.001

Figure 4: Seed-level margins: PPO vs best heuristic.

Seed-level normalised margins of PPO against the best per-seed heuristic across all four configurations on the held-out test split. Bars above zero indicate PPO wins. PPO remains predominantly positive across the flagship family, establishing learnability under the strongest heuristic comparator.

PPO’s advantage over the strongest heuristic is smallest in the more saturated service-composition settings and largest in the task-scheduling settings, where ties are much less common. The pattern is consistent with the broader validation logic: learnability strengthens as the benchmark becomes more discriminative.

5.6. Learnability: DDQN vs strongest heuristic

DDQN provides an informative contrast. Its mean QoS remains reasonably close to PPO’s, but the paired-seed evidence is more mixed when judged against the same strongest-per-seed heuristic comparator.

Table 11: DDQN vs best heuristic: paired test summary across experiments.

DDQN shows mixed paired-seed performance against the best per-seed heuristic across the four configurations (held-out test split, 100 paired seeds). The table reports win counts, median paired margins with 95% BCa confidence intervals, and one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank p -values with Holm correction across experiments.

Experiment	Wins	Median margin [95% BCa CI]	Wilc. p
Exp 1 (SC, Seq)	58	0.24% [-0.07%, 0.47%]	0.024
Exp 2 (SC, DAG)	40	-0.23% [-0.53%, -0.06%]	0.996
Exp 3 (TS, Seq)	60	0.44% [0.00%, 0.63%]	0.021
Exp 4 (TS, DAG)	65	0.40% [0.14%, 0.66%]	0.003

Figure 5: Seed-level margins: DDQN vs best heuristic.

Seed-level normalised margins of DDQN against the best per-seed heuristic across all four configurations on the held-out test split. Bars above zero indicate DDQN wins. DDQN remains competitive in several settings, but the evidence is materially less consistent than for PPO.

The contrast between Table 10 and fig. 4 and Table 11 and fig. 5 matters methodologically. It shows that the benchmark does not collapse all standard DRL probes into one undifferentiated performance profile.

5.7. Discernment: PPO vs DDQN

The final validation requirement is discernment: the ability to reveal meaningful differences between two materially different DRL probes under matched realised stochastic conditions. We therefore compare PPO and DDQN head-to-head on the same held-out seeds.

Table 12: PPO vs DDQN: paired summary across experiments.

Paired summary of PPO versus DDQN across all four configurations (held-out test split, 100 seeds). The table reports win counts, median paired margins with 95% BCa confidence intervals, and two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank results with Holm correction across experiments.

Experiment	Wins	Median margin [95% CI]	Wilc. p
Exp 1 (SC, Seq)	73	0.32% [0.17, 0.44]	< 0.001
Exp 2 (SC, DAG)	89	0.94% [0.76, 1.05]	< 0.001
Exp 3 (TS, Seq)	83	1.15% [0.77, 1.31]	< 0.001
Exp 4 (TS, DAG)	82	1.05% [0.69, 1.25]	< 0.001

Figure 6: Seed-level margins: PPO vs DDQN across experiments.

Seed-level normalised margins of PPO relative to DDQN across all four configurations on the held-out test split. Bars above zero indicate PPO wins and bars below zero indicate DDQN wins. PPO wins most seeds in every setting, but the size of its advantage remains regime-dependent.

Taken together, the validation results support the paper’s allowed claim. Under a fixed held-out protocol, the flagship `cmfg-gym` family is non-trivial, learnable, and sufficiently discerning to support later comparative DRL research. The evidence is strongest in the task-scheduling settings and more compressed in the more saturated service-composition regimes, especially SC, Seq, but the benchmark remains scientifically usable in precisely the bounded sense claimed here.

6. Discussion

The central result of this paper is methodological. `cmfg-gym` is shown to be hard enough to resist domination by simple heuristics, learnable by standard DRL agents, and sufficiently discerning to support later comparative claims under a held-out protocol. In a literature still constrained by fragmented formulations, uneven reproducibility, and implicit observability assumptions, that is already a substantive contribution. The immediate bottleneck in CMfg-DRL is not simply the absence of another novel architecture. It is the

absence of a shared empirical instrument for dynamic scheduling on which established and future methods can be compared like for like.

This matters because benchmark validity operates at a different level from algorithmic novelty. A private simulator can support an interesting local result. It cannot easily support cumulative field knowledge if later researchers cannot reconstruct the world, reproduce the stochastic contract, or determine what exactly was observable to the agent. A benchmark instrument, by contrast, contributes a stable experimental surface. In the present case, that surface includes a literature-derived architecture (UCSM), an executable environment (`cmfg-gym`), serialisable scenario files, explicit stochastic controls, and a fixed seed protocol. Those artefact surfaces are not auxiliary documentation. They are part of the scientific claim.

For computer-integrated manufacturing research, the practical value of that surface is that later dynamic-scheduling and control studies can reuse the same operational model of providers, services, jobs, and logistics while changing only the decision policy under test. That is the point at which comparison becomes cumulative rather than paper-local: the environment stops being hidden infrastructure and becomes part of the shared empirical object. For applied manufacturing-systems work, that instrument is most useful in the pre-pilot stage. It can support bounded decisions such as which policy families deserve deeper testing, whether partial observability is consequential enough to justify recurrent control, and whether an observed performance gain survives matched stochastic conditions before additional plant-specific modelling effort is committed. The scenario magnitudes admit a plausible operational reading, but the benchmark’s native scale remains abstract. It is therefore not claimed to be formally calibrated or statistically representative of cloud-manufacturing practice. The benchmark is correspondingly less suited to decisions that depend on detailed facility layout, richer logistics assets, contractual behaviour, or organisation-specific operating rules outside its scope.

The paper’s evidence remains intentionally bounded. The flagship family does not establish external validity for all CMfg settings, all logistics regimes, or all scales of industrial deployment. It also does not establish that every benchmark configuration is equally discriminative. The results suggest a more nuanced picture: task-scheduling settings provide the clearest separation, whereas the simpler service-composition settings are more saturation-prone and should therefore be interpreted with greater caution. Likewise, the reward comparison justifies one transparent benchmark design choice within

one tested setup; it does not imply a universal sparse-reward conclusion across algorithms or domains.

Several benchmark choices should be read in that same bounded way. The current environment uses a single logistics layer, fixed provider coordinates within an episode, one agent assignment decision per time step, and a particular provider-internal dispatch rule in service-composition mode. These choices are defensible because they make the benchmark explicit and reproducible while preserving the main CMfg trade-offs. Even so, they remain operational choices of the present instrument, not claims about the full ontology of CMfg scheduling. That distinction is precisely why separating UCSM from its operational instantiation matters. A final limitation concerns unit interpretation itself. In the current benchmark implementation, distances are Euclidean grid separations and travel time is computed from an abstract speed parameter. Realised processing and logistics durations are then executed in discrete simulation ticks. Practical interpretability in this paper therefore comes from coherent magnitudes and bounded face validity. It does not come from a formal software-level commitment to explicit industrial units.

The partial-observability framing has broader implications for later work. Because the environment makes the latent-state boundary explicit, future comparative studies can test questions that are currently difficult to ask fairly in the CMfg literature. These include feed-forward versus recurrent control, different masking and memory strategies, reward-shaping studies conducted on a fixed world model, and broader multi-instance generalisation protocols. Once the benchmark layer is stable, stronger algorithmic claims can begin to accumulate on common ground rather than on drifting local formulations.

There is also a practical implication for reproducibility culture in the field. Much CMfg-DRL work still reports environments primarily through prose descriptions. This paper argues for a different standard: the minimum reproducibility unit should be an executable environment package, fixed scenario artefacts, key non-default training settings, and a clearly defined seed contract.

In the current public release, that surface is exposed through the anchored repository version, fixed scenario witnesses, selected published probe checkpoints, and bounded workflow-integrity validation paths rather than through a full exact-from-scratch recomputation of every published Paper 1 statistic. If that standard becomes normal, later results will be easier to audit, reinterpret, and extend across computer-integrated manufacturing studies rather than remaining attached to isolated local simulators.

Several natural extensions remain future work. The most obvious are larger scenario suites, richer logistics models, delayed or noisy observations, within-episode topology change, multi-instance benchmark packs, and broader comparative cohorts that include recurrent and memory-augmented agents. Those are important next steps, but they depend on first having an instrument layer robust enough to support them. The present paper is intended to provide that starting point.

7. Conclusion

This paper has argued that cumulative DRL research in Cloud Manufacturing is currently limited mainly by methodology rather than by a lack of new algorithms. The literature already contains recurring dynamic-scheduling structure in CMfg, but it still lacks a sufficiently common empirical object for reliable like-for-like comparison. To address that gap, the paper introduced the Unified Cloud Manufacturing Scheduling Model (UCSM), operationalised it as the reproducible, POMDP-consistent environment `cmfg-gym`, and validated one flagship environment family under a fixed held-out protocol with two standard DRL probes.

The resulting claim is deliberately narrow but important. What we do show is that one explicit, literature-derived, reproducible CMfg environment family is non-trivial, learnable, and sufficiently discerning to function as a reusable benchmark instrument for later comparative DRL research on dynamic scheduling in CMfg. Under that bounded validation contract, PPO beats the strongest per-seed heuristic across the flagship family, DDQN remains competitive but less consistent against that comparator, and the clearest PPO–DDQN separation appears in task scheduling. The more saturated service-composition settings should therefore be read more cautiously than the task-scheduling results.

That public benchmark surface should be read in the same bounded way as the paper’s empirical claim: the released repository exposes an auditable witness slice and workflow-validation path for Paper 1, not a claim of full exact-from-scratch recomputation from the cleaned public repo alone.

The broader implication is straightforward. Once the instrument layer is fixed, later CMfg-DRL studies can argue about algorithms on common ground rather than on drifting local problem worlds. For computer-integrated manufacturing research, that means dispatching, control, and learning policies

can be evaluated against a shared operational model rather than against paper-specific simulators. That is the paper’s main contribution: not another local scheduler result, but a reusable empirical basis for more reliable comparison in computer-integrated manufacturing research. In short, the benchmark is intended to support early-stage policy screening and reproducible comparative evaluation for distributed CMfg scheduling in an operationally readable but still stylised setting, while leaving deployment-grade plant modelling to later, higher-fidelity studies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

David Chambers: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Visualization, Writing - original draft. Thorsten Lammers: Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing. Kun Yu: Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing. Nathan Chambers: Software, Validation, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used OpenAI generative AI tools to support language editing, structural revision, and document organisation. The authors reviewed and edited the resulting text carefully and take full responsibility for the content of this manuscript.

Data availability

The `cmfg-gym` environment, the fixed flagship scenario artefacts `slc_balanced.json` and `paper_artifacts/paper1/slc_balanced_witness.json`, the retained published probe checkpoints, and the train/evaluation/test seed protocol used in this study are available through the public project repository at <https://github.com/ergosphere-ai/cmfg-gym>. This preprint is

archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20222612>. The minimum reproducibility unit for the reported validation results is the anchored repository version, those scenario files, the declared seed blocks, the retained witness checkpoints, and the runtime settings described in the manuscript. The current public release supports bounded witness- and workflow-based validation of the Paper 1 results; it does not claim a full exact-from-scratch recomputation of every published statistic from the public repo alone.

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